

Developing E-Pharmacy Platform for Disabled and Elderly Individuals

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ABSTRACT

In this study, a web based social platform, Medication Assistance Web Platform or e-pharmacy in short, meeting the medication needs of elderly and disabled individuals was developed. The system allows the users to receive medication support and supports collaboration mechanism by providing rewards such as badges, points and certificates. The platform was developed using a secure and scalable software architecture and intended to increase the accessibility for the targeted individuals by providing a user-friendly interface. An effective digital infrastructure was developed by prioritizing database management, user authentication systems and data security. In this way, users' information will be kept confidential. In addition, the platform helps the individuals to receive their medications more quickly and accurately by optimizing the donation processes by using artificial intelligence supported recommendation systems. By using the pilot application, the efficiency of the platform was tested and the system was optimized by using the users' feedbacks.

ARTICLE INFO

Received 09.10.2025,

Accepted 12.11.2025,

Publication Date 15.12.2025

Keywords:

e-pharmacy, web-based platform, medication, AI supported systems, data safety, medication accessibility, health technologies.

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Engelli ve Yaşlı Bireyler için E-Pharmacy Platformu Geliştirme

ÖZET

Bu çalışmada, yaşlı ve engelli bireylerin ilaç ihtiyaçlarını karşılayan, web tabanlı bir sosyal platform olan İlaç Yardımı Web Platformu veya kısaca e-eczane geliştirilmiştir. Sistem, kullanıcılara ilaç desteği alma olanağı sunmakta ve rozet, puan ve sertifika gibi ödüller sağlayarak iş birliği mekanizmasını desteklemektedir. Platform, güvenli ve ölçeklenebilir bir yazılım mimarisi kullanılarak geliştirilmiş olup, kullanıcı dostu bir arayüz sağlayarak hedef kitleye erişilebilirliği artırmayı amaçlamaktadır. Veritabanı yönetimi, kullanıcı kimlik doğrulama sistemleri ve veri güvenliğine öncelik verilerek etkili bir dijital altyapı geliştirilmiştir. Bu sayede kullanıcı bilgilerinin gizliliği korunacaktır. Ayrıca, platform, yapay zeka destekli öneri sistemleri kullanarak bağış süreçlerini optimize ederek bireylerin ilaçlarını daha hızlı ve doğru bir şekilde almalarına yardımcı olmaktadır. Pilot uygulama kullanılarak platformun verimliliği test edilmiş ve kullanıcı geri bildirimleri kullanılarak sistem optimize edilmiştir.

MAKALE BİLGİSİ

Gönderi 09.10.2025,

Kabul 12.11.2025,

Yayınlama Tarihi 15.12.2025

Keywords:

e-eczane, web tabanlı platform, ilaç, yapay zeka destekli sistemler, veri güvenliği, ilaç erişilebilirliği, sağlık teknolojileri.

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INTRODUCTION

It is known that elderly and disabled individuals experience great difficulties in obtaining the medications they need to use regularly. The research aims to increase social solidarity and increase the motivation of individuals to help by developing a web platform to meet the medication needs of individuals. Some of these approaches are evaluated as platforms known as e-pharmacy. Due to the increase in the average age rate in our age, the importance of e-pharmacy platforms is increasing due to the need for effective and accessible health services. Lack of accessibility of medication causes series hospitalization and even deaths. In a study conducted by Ho et al., patients with diabetes mellitus experienced serious outcomes due to medication accessibility related problems (Ho et al., 2006). In their study, it was found that those patients exhibited higher hospitalization rates (23.2% vs. 19.2%) and mortality rates (5.9% vs. 4.0%) compared to the patients without any problems on their accessibility for medications. Suhirman et al. (2021) found in their study that online pharmacy platforms showed high success in timely medicine distribution (Suhirman et al., 2021). They stated that errors were reduced and general system reliability was ensured, especially with the documentation approach. In another study, Wang and Xing (2016) created a program that recorded user interactions and showed its applicability to automated systems in a specific treatment

planning (Wang & Xing, 2016). Their approach increased planning and efficiency in medical treatment applications, as well as increasing the accuracy in clinical approaches. Such studies prove the positive effects of the applications of health services connected to online pharmacies. Again in 2025, Agudelo et al. In a study conducted by Burk et al., the potential for improving continuity of pharmacy practices and patient feedback is emphasized (Agudelo et al., 2025). The results they found show that digital solutions will become increasingly widespread, especially in optimizing medicine treatment and access to medicines. On the other hand, a study on the use of web applications in decision-making mechanisms involving pharmacies and patient safety was conducted by Burk et al. in 2013 (Burk et al., 2013). This study indicates the benefits of using digital tools for medicine management in health systems. It is clear that the hospitalization rate and the mortality will be reduced by using the suggested platform particularly for patients having difficulties on recording, accessing and obtaining their regular/irregular medications on time. This study offers a different model among social responsibility projects, providing faster and more effective medicine supply to those in need through volunteers. Furthermore, a social assistance web platform supported by a reward mechanism can increase the motivation of individuals to be helpful and provide faster access to those in need. In this way, the organization, sustainability and optimization of treatments based on medication distribution/accessibility will be provided more effectively.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

While developing the web platform, scoring and rewarding systems were developed in the system about the cooperation of the elderly and disabled patients. In order to optimize the functionality and user experience of the system, several tests were performed with the patients and necessary optimizations were conducted by receiving feedbacks from the test group of the patients including both elderly, disabled and elderly-disabled patients. For these tests, informed consent forms were distributed to the test group and their consents were obtained before the application of the tests. The system developed in this study aims to facilitate medicine sharing by bringing together those in need and volunteer donors on a digital platform. The application includes user login processes, identity verification, creating a medication need, making a donation, an administrator approval process, and reward mechanisms such as points/badges. The system architecture is developed according to three basic roles: user, donor, and administrator. The flowchart presented below (Figure 1) shows the platform's operating process. In the diagram, the path followed by users from login to medication selection, donation, approval, and document creation steps is also visualized together with administrators' approval and statistics processes on the system. Thanks to this structure, both the user experience is increased and the transaction processes are simplified.

Figure 1. Flowchart of e-pharmacy application

The flowchart in Figure 1 shows the general operating logic of the system and how the processes progress according to user roles. In the diagram, the request creation process of individuals in need of medicine is detailed on the left side, the drug selection and donation steps of volunteer users are detailed in the middle, and the approval and system management processes of administrators are detailed on the right side. At the end of the process, donation documents are generated, the users are rewarded with points and badges, and communication is supported with in-system messaging. The Medication Assistance Web Platform was developed to help elderly and disabled individuals to overcome the difficulties they are facing in obtaining medication and to help them to promote social help. The platform was developed by using ASP.NET Core MVC. Since the main goal of the platform is to help elderly and disabled individuals in need of medicine to receive support from volunteers. The system includes modules that allow individuals in need to record their requests, volunteers to respond to these requests in a timely manner and inform both parties. The current system components can be divided into 5 sections as shown in the following figure.

Figure 2. System Components

i. User Management

The platform includes a comprehensive user management system in which users can register, login and manage their profile information. In order to keep dynamic functionality, the user management section is composed of the following three items.

- Registration System: Allows new users to register to the system
- Login System: Allows existing users to log in
- Profile Management: Allows users to view and edit their personal information.

The program for this part includes login, registration, username/email uniqueness checks, session handling via a helper class and redirects which are the general approach and stable solutions for user management section of the platform.

ii. Medicine Needs Module

This module allows the formation, listing and display of detailed information of medicine requirements. This module requires the formation of *generating needs*, *listing needs* and *need details* section. These parts are used to send medicine requests for those in need, to list current medication requests and to view details of a specific medicine request. In the first part for preparing the program for generating needs section, a widely adopted architecture in ASP.NET Core MVC, including session-based access control and LINQ-based database querying were used. Even though the technical structure was established using the best approaches in the field, the integration of these elements in such a real-life problem (e-pharmacy) can be considered as one of the novel aspect of our study.

iii. Donation Module

In order to fulfill the donation purpose of the platform, this module allowing users to donate medications according to the listed needs, view their donation history and download their donation documents. For this purpose, three options were included. These options are *Donate*, *Donation History* and *Donation Document Generation* section. These separate functions allows users to donate to a specific medicine need, to investigate their previous donations and to generate donation documents as the name stands. A simple donation document can be seen in the Figure 2(c).

Figure 3. Generating Donation Report. (a) File accumulation location, (b) Sample donation report

iv. Messaging Module

As expected, this module provides secure communication between users. The module includes; Send Message, List Message and Messaging History sections.

v. Admin Panel

The panel is responsible of providing management of the platform. The panel includes Users, People in need of medication, medication needs and donations. The user friendly version of the Admin panel is given in the following figure.

Figure 4. Admin Panel User View

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Pilot application of the developed medication aid web platform was performed with a user group of 15 people including elderly, disabled and voluntary patients. This test process was carried out in a controlled environment in order to assess the usability, effectiveness and security of the system. The distribution of the participants' profiles can be seen in the following table (Table 1).

Table 1 Participants' Profiles for Pilot Study

Participants' Profiles		
Gender	Middle Age	Elderly
Male	2	3
Female	6	4

During the pilot application, participants successfully completed basic operations such as creating a user registration, creating a drug request, donating and producing a donation document. In line with the feedback collected from the participants, the simple and understandable structure of the user interface was welcomed. More than 90% of the participants stated that they were able to use the system effectively without needing external assistance. To include the effect of education levels of the users, the education levels of the participants were also collected (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Education level distribution of the participants for the pilot study

The badge and point-based reward mechanism in the system has been evaluated as a motivational factor, especially by volunteer users. Authentication modules such as login and session management have been tested against common security vulnerabilities and no critical vulnerabilities have been detected. The participants were asked to fill out a Likert Scale Survey representing the effectiveness of the platform. The questions asked are listed below and they were asked to grade the questions from 1 to 5 representing unsatisfied to very satisfied.

Table 2 Survey questions

Question #	Survey Item
1	The overall interface of the platform was easy to use.
2	The process of forming a medication request was straightforward and simple.
3	The voluntary donation system was easy to use.
4	The messaging feature can met patient's needs.
5	The reward system (badges, points, etc.) was motivating.
6	I found the system security sufficient.
7	I am satisfied with the overall system.

In the evaluations carried out by technical performance; the average system response time for user transactions (logging in, sending requests, making donations, etc.) has been measured as less than 500 milliseconds, which is within acceptable limits for modern web applications. In addition, database operations performed with LINQ-based queries were performed without any significant delay even in simultaneous multi-user scenarios. The ability to monitor user interactions, approve medication requests, and manage in-system messaging functions effectively via the admin panel has been enabled. The flow-based design of the panel has allowed administrators to monitor the overall situation quickly and effectively.

The average score of the responses given by the participants are given in the following figure. One can see from the figure that the participants are satisfied the most on registering a medication request and least satisfied with the messaging features which will be improved accordingly.

Figure 6. Average scores of the participants for the survey

The findings show that the platform not only facilitates access to medication but also encourages a culture of social cooperation and solidarity. These results are consistent with studies in literature that emphasize the potential of digital solutions to increase access to healthcare services.

However, some areas for improvement were also identified during the pilot application process. Users with visual impairments requested that fonts be enlarged and contrast themes be developed. In this context, dark mode and dynamic font size options are in the process of being integrated into the system as part of accessibility improvements. In addition, in the upcoming stages, it is planned to match donors with recipients more effectively based on location and medication type with an artificial intelligence-supported matching mechanism.

As a result, the developed platform offers a strong example of a digital solution in terms of its functionality, scalability and social impact. It was shown from the user feedbacks that the system is user friendly and effective for those who needs assistance to access their medication.

Furthermore, the effectiveness of the system can be further increased with continuous updates based on user feedback of larger groups.

CONCLUSION

The Medication Assistance Web Platform is being developed to help elderly and disabled individuals overcome the difficulties they face in the process of obtaining medicine and to promote social solidarity. The platform aims to ensure effective participation of users with its user-friendly interface, secure infrastructure and motivation mechanisms. The platform was tested using a study group of 15 people including elderly patients, disabled people and voluntary individuals. According to the feedback received from the study group, the platform was optimized. It should also be noted that the success of the platform depends on the strength of the technical infrastructure as well as the strengthening of the culture of social participation and solidarity.

The Medication Assistance Web Platform is an innovative example of how digital technologies can be effectively used to solve social problems. Beyond reducing inequalities in access to medicine, the platform also contributes to the building of social solidarity and trust.

REFERENCES

- Agudelo, R., Pereañez, J. A., Correa Muñoz, S. M., Granados, J., & Ceballos, M. (2025). e-Health applications for outpatient professional pharmaceutical care services: A scoping review. *Exploratory Research in Clinical and Social Pharmacy*, 17, 100567. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcsop.2025.100567>
- Burk, M., Moore, V., Glassman, P., Good, C., Emmendorfer, T., Leadholm, T., & Cunningham, F. (2013). Medication-use evaluation with a Web application. *American Journal of Health-System Pharmacy*, 70(24), 2226-2234. <https://doi.org/10.2146/ajhp130252>
- Ho, P. M., Rumsfeld, J. S., Masoudi, F. A., McClure, D. L., Plomondon, M. E., Steiner, J. F., & Magid, D. J. (2006). Effect of medication nonadherence on hospitalization and mortality among patients with diabetes mellitus. *Archives of Internal Medicine*, 166(17), 1836-1841. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archinte.166.17.1836>
- Suhrman, S., Tri Hidayat, A., Saputra, W., & Saifullah, S. (2021). Website-Based E-Pharmacy Application Development to Improve Sales Services Using Waterfall Method. *International Journal of Advances in Data and Information Systems*, 2(2), 114-129. <https://doi.org/10.25008/ijadis.v2i2.1226>
- Wang, H., & Xing, L. (2016). Application programming in C# environment with recorded user software interactions and its application in autopilot of VMAT/IMRT treatment planning. *Journal of Applied Clinical Medical Physics*, 17(6), 189-203. <https://doi.org/10.1120/jacmp.v17i6.6425>